

Neutrosophic Refined Relations and Their Properties

Said Broumi, Irfan Deli, Florentin Smarandache

Abstract

In this paper, the neutrosophic refined relation (NRR) defined on the neutrosophic refined sets(multisets) [13] is introduced. Various properties like reflexivity, symmetry and transitivity are studied.

Keyword 0.1 *Neutrosophic sets, neutrosophic refined sets, neutrosophic refined relations, reflexivity, symmetry, transitivity.*

1 Introduction

Recently, several theories have been proposed to deal with uncertainty, imprecision and vagueness. Theory of probability, fuzzy set theory[18], intuitionistic fuzzy sets[17], rough set theory[49] etc. are consistently being utilized as efficient tools for dealing with diverse types of uncertainties and imprecision embedded in a system. But, all these above theories failed to deal with indeterminate and inconsistent information which exist in beliefs system. In 1995, inspired from the sport games (winning/tie/defeating), from votes (yes/ NA/ no), from decision making (making a decision/ hesitating/not making) etc. and guided by the fact that the law of excluded middle did not work any longer in the modern logics, F. Smarandache[10] developed a new concept called neutrosophic set (NS) which generalizes fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets. NS can be described by membership degree, indeterminate degree and non-membership degree. This theory and their hybrid structures have proven useful in many different fields such as control theory[32], databases[20, 21], medical diagnosis problem[1], decision making problem [24, 2], physics[8], topology [9], etc. The works on neutrosophic set, in theories and applications, have been progressing rapidly (e.g. [3, 6, 35, 41, 48, 19]).

Combining neutrosophic set models with other mathematical models has attracted the attention of many researchers. Maji et al.[22] presented the concept of neutrosophic soft sets which is based on a combination of the neutrosophic set and soft set models. Broumi and Smarandache[33, 36] introduced the concept of the intuitionistic neutrosophic soft set by combining the intuitionistic neutrosophic sets and soft sets. Broumi et al. presented the concept of rough neutrosophic set[39] which is based on a combination of neutrosophic sets and rough set models. The works on neutrosophic sets combining with soft sets, in theories and applications, have been progressing rapidly (e.g. [34, 37, 38, 14, 15, 40, 16, 42]).

The notion of multisets was formulated first in [31] by Yager as generalization of the concept of set theory and then the multiset was developed in [7] by Calude et al. Several authors from time to time made a number of generalizations of the multiset theory. For example, Sebastian and Ramakrishnan[46, 45] introduced a new notion called multi fuzzy sets, which is a generalization of the multiset. Since then, Several researchers [30, 44, 4, 5] discussed more properties on multi fuzzy set. And they [47, 23] made an extension of the concept of Fuzzy multisets to an intuitionistic fuzzy set, which was called intuitionistic fuzzy multisets (IFMS). Since then in the study on IFMS, a lot of excellent results have been achieved by researchers [43, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. An element of a multi fuzzy set can occur more than once with possibly the same or different membership values, whereas an element of intuitionistic fuzzy multiset allows the repeated occurrences of membership and non-membership values. The concepts of FMS and IFMS fail to deal with indeterminacy. In 2013 Smarandache [11] extended the classical neutrosophic logic to n-valued refined neutrosophic logic, by refining each neutrosophic component T, I, F into respectively T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m , and I_1, I_2, \dots, I_p , and F_1, F_2, \dots, F_r . Recently, Deli et al.[13] used the concept of neutrosophic refined sets and studied some of their basic properties. The concept of neutrosophic refined set (NRS) is a generalization of fuzzy multisets and intuitionistic fuzzy multisets.

The neutrosophic refined relations are the neutrosophic refined subsets in a cartesian product of the universe. The purpose of this paper is an attempt to extend the neutrosophic relations to neutrosophic refined relations (NRR). This paper is arranged in the following manner. In section 2, we present some definitions of neutrosophic set and neutrosophic refined set theory which help us in the later section. In section 3, we study the concept of neutrosophic refined relations and their operations. Finally, we conclude the paper.

2 Preliminary

In this section, we mainly recall some notions related to neutrosophic set [10], single valued neutrosophic set (SVNS) [12] and neutrosophic refined set relevant to the present work. See especially [20, 21, 1, 3, 6, 35, 24, 2, 9, 8, 12] for further details and background.

Smarandache [11] refine T, I, F to T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m and I_1, I_2, \dots, I_p and F_1, F_2, \dots, F_r where all T_m, I_p and F_r can be subset of $[0,1]$. In the following sections, we considered only the case when T, I and F are split into the same number of subcomponents $1, 2, \dots, p$, and T_A^j, I_A^j, F_A^j are single valued neutrosophic number.

Definition 2.1 [10] *Let U be a space of points (objects), with a generic element in U denoted by u . A neutrosophic set (N-set) A in U is characterized by a truth-membership function T_A , a indeterminacy-membership function I_A and a falsity-membership function F_A . $T_A(x); I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-0, 1^+}$. It can be written as*

$$A = \{ \langle u, (T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) \rangle : x \in E, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in]^{-0, 1^+} \}.$$

There is no restriction on the sum of $T_A(x); I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$, so $^{-0} \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^+$.

For application in real scientific and engineering areas, Wang et al. [12] proposed the concept of an SVNS, which is an instance of neutrosophic set. In the following, we introduce the definition of SVNS.

Definition 2.2 [12] *Let U be a space of points (objects), with a generic element in U denoted by u . An SVNS A in X is characterized by a truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, a indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$ and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$, where $T_A(x), I_A(x)$, and $F_A(x)$ belongs to $[0,1]$ for each point u in U . Then, an SVNS A can be expressed as*

$$A = \{ \langle u, (T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) \rangle : x \in E, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1] \}.$$

There is no restriction on the sum of $T_A(x); I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$, so $0 \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.3 [13] *Let E be a universe. A neutrosophic refined set (NRS) A on E can be defined as follows:*

$$A = \{ \langle x, (T_A^1(x), T_A^2(x), \dots, T_A^P(x)), (I_A^1(x), I_A^2(x), \dots, I_A^P(x)), (F_A^1(x), F_A^2(x), \dots, F_A^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

where,

$$T_A^1(x), T_A^2(x), \dots, T_A^P(x) : E \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

$$I_A^1(x), I_A^2(x), \dots, I_A^P(x) : E \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

and

$$F_A^1(x), F_A^2(x), \dots, F_A^P(x) : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$0 \leq \sup T_A^i(x) + \sup I_A^i(x) + \sup F_A^i(x) \leq 3$$

($i = 1, 2, \dots, P$) and

$$T_A^1(x) \leq T_A^2(x) \leq \dots \leq T_A^P(x)$$

for any $x \in E$.

$(T_A^1(x), T_A^2(x), \dots, T_A^P(x))$, $(I_A^1(x), I_A^2(x), \dots, I_A^P(x))$ and $(F_A^1(x), F_A^2(x), \dots, F_A^P(x))$ is the truth-membership sequence, indeterminacy-membership sequence and falsity-membership sequence of the element x , respectively. Also, P is called the dimension(cardinality) of NRS A . We arrange the truth-membership sequence in decreasing order but the corresponding indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership sequence may not be in decreasing or increasing order.

The set of all Neutrosophic refined sets on E is denoted by $NRS(E)$.

Definition 2.4 [13] Let $A, B \in NRS(E)$. Then,

1. A is said to be NR subset of B is denoted by $A \tilde{\subseteq} B$ if $T_A^i(x) \leq T_B^i(x)$, $I_A^i(x) \geq I_B^i(x)$, $F_A^i(x) \geq F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$.
2. A is said to be neutrosophic equal of B is denoted by $A = B$ if $T_A^i(x) = T_B^i(x)$, $I_A^i(x) = I_B^i(x)$, $F_A^i(x) = F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$.
3. the complement of A denoted by $A^{\tilde{c}}$ and is defined by

$$A^{\tilde{c}} = \{ \langle x, (F_A^1(x), F_A^2(x), \dots, F_A^P(x)), (I_A^1(x), I_A^2(x), \dots, I_A^P(x)), (T_A^1(x), T_A^2(x), \dots, T_A^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

4. If $T_A^i(x) = 0$ and $I_A^i(x) = F_A^i(x) = 1$ for all $x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$ then A is called null ns-set and denoted by $\tilde{\Phi}$.
5. If $T_A^i(x) = 1$ and $I_A^i(x) = F_A^i(x) = 0$ for all $x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$, then A is called universal ns-set and denoted by \tilde{E} .

Definition 2.5 [13] Let $A, B \in NRS(E)$. Then,

1. the union of A and B is denoted by $A \tilde{\cup} B = C_1$ and is defined by

$$C = \{ \langle x, (T_C^1(x), T_C^2(x), \dots, T_C^P(x)), (I_C^1(x), I_C^2(x), \dots, I_C^P(x)), (F_C^1(x), F_C^2(x), \dots, F_C^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

where $T_C^i = T_A^i(x) \vee T_B^i(x)$, $I_C^i = I_A^i(x) \wedge I_B^i(x)$, $F_C^i = F_A^i(x) \wedge F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

2. the intersection of A and B is denoted by $A \widetilde{\cap} B = D$ and is defined by

$$D = \{ \langle x, (T_D^1(x), T_D^2(x), \dots, T_D^P(x)), (I_D^1(x), I_D^2(x), \dots, I_D^P(x)), (F_D^1(x), F_D^2(x), \dots, F_D^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

where $T_D^i = T_A^i(x) \wedge T_B^i(x)$, $I_D^i = I_A^i(x) \vee I_B^i(x)$, $F_D^i = F_A^i(x) \vee F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

3. the addition of A and B is denoted by $A \widetilde{+} B = E_1$ and is defined by

$$E_1 = \{ \langle x, (T_{E_1}^1(x), T_{E_1}^2(x), \dots, T_{E_1}^P(x)), (I_{E_1}^1(x), I_{E_1}^2(x), \dots, I_{E_1}^P(x)), (F_{E_1}^1(x), F_{E_1}^2(x), \dots, F_{E_1}^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

where $T_{E_1}^i = T_A^i(x) + T_B^i(x) - T_A^i(x) \cdot T_B^i(x)$, $I_{E_1}^i = I_A^i(x) \cdot I_B^i(x)$, $F_{E_1}^i = F_A^i(x) \cdot F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

4. the multiplication of A and B is denoted by $A \widetilde{\times} B = E_2$ and is defined by

$$E_2 = \{ \langle x, (T_{E_2}^1(x), T_{E_2}^2(x), \dots, T_{E_2}^P(x)), (I_{E_2}^1(x), I_{E_2}^2(x), \dots, I_{E_2}^P(x)), (F_{E_2}^1(x), F_{E_2}^2(x), \dots, F_{E_2}^P(x)) \rangle : x \in E \}$$

where $T_{E_2}^i = T_A^i(x) \cdot T_B^i(x)$, $I_{E_2}^i = I_A^i(x) + I_B^i(x) - I_A^i(x) \cdot I_B^i(x)$, $F_{E_2}^i = F_A^i(x) + F_B^i(x) - F_A^i(x) \cdot F_B^i(x)$, $\forall x \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, P$.

Here $\vee, \wedge, +, \cdot, -$ denotes maximum, minimum, addition, multiplication, subtraction of real numbers respectively.

3 Relations on Neutrosophic Refined Sets

In this section, after given the Cartesian product of two neutrosophic refined sets (NRS), we define a relations on neutrosophic refined sets and study their desired properties. The relation extend the concept of intuitionistic multirelation [27] to single valued neutrosophic refined relation. Some of it is quoted from [13, 27, 10].

Definition 3.1 Let $\emptyset \neq A, B \in NRS(E)$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then, cartesian product of A and B is a neutrosophic refined set in $E \times E$, denoted by $A \times B$, defined as

$$A \times B = \{ \langle (x, y), (T_{A \times B}^j(x, y)), (I_{A \times B}^j(x, y), F_{A \times B}^j(x, y)) \rangle : (x, y) \in E \times E \}$$

where

$$T_{A \times B}^j(x, y), I_{A \times B}^j(x, y), F_{A \times B}^j(x, y) : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

,

$$T_{A \times B}^j(x, y) = \min \{ T_A^j(x), T_B^j(x) \},$$

$$I_{A \times B}^j(x, y) = \max \{ I_A^j(x), I_B^j(x) \}$$

and

$$F_{A \times B}^j(x, y) = \max \{ F_A^j(x), F_B^j(x) \}$$

for all $x, y \in E$.

Remark 3.2 A Cartesian product on A is a neutrosophic refined set in $E \times E$, denoted by $A \times A$, defined as

$$A \times A = \{ \langle (x, y), T_{A \times A}^j(x, y), I_{A \times A}^j(x, y), F_{A \times A}^j(x, y) \rangle : (x, y) \in E \times E \}$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $T_{A \times A}^j, I_{A \times A}^j, F_{A \times A}^j : E \times E \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Example 3.3 Let $E = \{x_1, x_2\}$ be a universal set and A and B be two Nm-sets over E as;

$$A = \{ \langle x_1, \{0.3, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle x_2, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.1\}, \{0.6, 0.2, 0.7\} \rangle \}$$

and

$$B = \{ \langle x_1, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.4, 0.4\}, \{0.3, 0.8, 0.4\} \rangle, \langle x_2, \{0.6, 0.7, 0.8\}, \{0.3, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.1, 0.7, 0.6\} \rangle \}$$

Then, the cartesian product of A and B is obtained as follows

$$A \times B = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.3, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.4, 0.4\}, \{0.3, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.3, 0.7, 0.8\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.1, 0.7, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.4\}, \{0.3, 0.8, 0.7\} \rangle, \langle (x_2, x_2), \{0.4, 0.7, 0.8\}, \{0.3, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.1, 0.7, 0.7\} \rangle \}$$

Definition 3.4 Let $\emptyset \neq A, B \in NRS(E)$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Then, a neutrosophic refined relation from A to B is a neutrosophic refined subset of $A \times B$. In other words, a neutrosophic refined relation from A to B is of the form (R, C) , $(C \subseteq E \times E)$ where $R(x, y) \subseteq A \times B \forall (x, y) \in C$.

Example 3.5 Let us consider the Example 3.3. Then, we define a neutrosophic refined relation R and S , from A to B , as follows

$$R = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.2, 0.6, 0.9\}, \{0.2, 0.4, 0.5\}, \{0.3, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.3, 0.9, 0.8\}, \{0.2, 0.8, 0.7\}, \{0.1, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.1, 0.9, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.4\}, \{0.2, 0.8, 0.7\} \rangle \}$$

and

$$S = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.1, 0.7, 0.9\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.1, 0.9, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.3, 0.9, 0.8\}, \{0.2, 0.8, 0.8\}, \{0.1, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.1, 0.9, 0.7\}, \{0.2, 0.9, 0.4\}, \{0.2, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle \}$$

Definition 3.6 Let $A, B \in NRS(E)$ and, R and S be two neutrosophic refined relation from A to B . Then, the operations $R\cup S$, $R\tilde{\cap}S$, $R\tilde{+}S$ and $R\tilde{\times}S$ are defined as follows;

1.

$$R\tilde{\cup}S = \{ \langle (x, y), (T_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^1(x, y), T_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^2(x, y), \dots, T_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (I_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^1(x, y), I_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^2(x, y), \dots, I_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (F_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^1(x, y), F_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^2(x, y), \dots, F_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^n(x, y)) \rangle : x, y \in E \}$$

where

$$T_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^i(x, y) = T_R^i(x) \vee T_S^i(y), \\ I_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^i(x, y) = I_R^i(x) \wedge I_S^i(y), \\ F_{R\tilde{\cup}S}^i(x, y) = F_R^i(x) \wedge F_S^i(y)$$

$\forall x, y \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

2.

$$R\tilde{\cap}S = \{ \langle (x, y), (T_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^1(x, y), T_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^2(x, y), \dots, T_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (I_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^1(x, y), I_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^2(x, y), \dots, I_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (F_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^1(x, y), F_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^2(x, y), \dots, F_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^n(x, y)) \rangle : x, y \in E \}$$

where

$$T_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^i(x, y) = T_R^i(x) \wedge T_S^i(y), \\ I_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^i(x, y) = I_R^i(x) \vee I_S^i(y), \\ F_{R\tilde{\cap}S}^i(x, y) = F_R^i(x) \vee F_S^i(y)$$

$\forall x, y \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

3.

$$R\tilde{+}S = \{ \langle (x, y), (T_{R\tilde{+}S}^1(x, y), T_{R\tilde{+}S}^2(x, y), \dots, T_{R\tilde{+}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (I_{R\tilde{+}S}^1(x, y), I_{R\tilde{+}S}^2(x, y), \dots, I_{R\tilde{+}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (F_{R\tilde{+}S}^1(x, y), F_{R\tilde{+}S}^2(x, y), \dots, F_{R\tilde{+}S}^n(x, y)) \rangle : x, y \in E \}$$

where

$$T_{R\tilde{+}S}^i(x, y) = T_R^i(x) + T_S^i(y) - T_R^i(x).T_S^i(y), \\ I_{R\tilde{+}S}^i(x, y) = I_R^i(x).I_S^i(y), \\ F_{R\tilde{+}S}^i(x, y) = F_R^i(x).F_S^i(y)$$

$\forall x, y \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

4.

$$R\tilde{\times}S = \{ \langle (x, y), (T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^1(x, y), T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^2(x, y), \dots, T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^1(x, y), I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^2(x, y), \dots, I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^n(x, y)), \\ (F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^1(x, y), F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^2(x, y), \dots, F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^n(x, y)) \rangle : x, y \in E \}$$

where

$$T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^i(x, y) = T_R^i(x).T_S^i(y), \\ I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^i(x, y) = I_R^i(x) + I_S^i(y) - I_R^i(x).I_S^i(y), \\ F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^i(x, y) = F_R^i(x) + F_S^i(y) - F_R^i(x).F_S^i(y)$$

$\forall x, y \in E$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Here $\vee, \wedge, +, \cdot, -$ denotes maximum, minimum, addition, multiplication, subtraction of real numbers respectively.

Example 3.7 Let us consider the two neutrosophic refined relation R and S , from A to B , as follows

$$R = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.3, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.3, 0.4, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.5, 0.6, 0.7\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.1, 0.6, 0.3\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\} \rangle \}$$

and

$$S = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.1, 0.4, 0.5\}, \{0.3, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.2, 0.7, 0.1\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.5, 0.6, 0.7\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.6\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.1, 0.2, 0.3\} \rangle \}$$

Then,

$$R\tilde{\cup}S = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.3, 0.7, 0.1\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.3, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.5, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.5, 0.3, 0.6\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.4, 0.5, 0.3\}, \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}, \{0.2, 0.2, 0.3\} \rangle \}$$

and

$$R\tilde{\cap}S = \{ \langle (x_1, x_1), \{0.1, 0.4, 0.5\}, \{0.3, 0.5, 0.7\}, \{0.2, 0.8, 0.9\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_1, x_2), \{0.2, 0.4, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.6, 0.7\}, \{0.2, 0.6, 0.6\} \rangle, \\ \langle (x_2, x_1), \{0.1, 0.6, 0.6\}, \{0.2, 0.5, 0.6\}, \{0.1, 0.3, 0.4\} \rangle \}$$

Assume that $\emptyset \neq A, B, C \in NRS(E)$. Two neutrosophic refined relations under a suitable composition, could too yield a new neutrosophic refined relation with a useful significance. Composition of relations is important for applications, because of the reason that if a relation on A and B is known and if a relation on B and C is known then the relation on A and C could be computed and defined as follows;

Definition 3.8 Let $R(A \rightarrow B)$ and $S(B \rightarrow C)$ be two neutrosophic refined relations. The composition $S \circ R$ is a neutrosophic refined relation from A to C , defined by

$$S \circ R = \left\langle (x, z), (T_{S \circ R}^1(x, z), T_{S \circ R}^2(x, z), \dots, T_{S \circ R}^n(x, z)), \right. \\ \left. (I_{S \circ R}^1(x, z), I_{S \circ R}^2(x, z), \dots, I_{S \circ R}^n(x, z)), \right. \\ \left. (F_{S \circ R}^1(x, z), F_{S \circ R}^2(x, z), \dots, F_{S \circ R}^n(x, z)) \right\rangle : x, z \in E$$

where

$$T_{S \circ R}^j(x, z) = \bigvee_y \left\{ T_R^j(x, y) \wedge T_S^j(y, z) \right\}$$

$$I_{S \circ R}^j(x, z) = \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_R^j(x, y) \vee I_S^j(y, z) \right\}$$

and

$$F_{S \circ R}^j(x, z) = \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_R^j(x, y) \vee F_S^j(y, z) \right\}$$

for every $(x, z) \in E \times E$, for every $y \in E$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Definition 3.9 A neutrosophic refined relation R on A is said to be;

1. reflexive if $T_R^j(x, x) = 1, I_R^j(x, x) = 0$ and $F_R^j(x, x) = 0$ for all $x \in E$
2. symmetric if $T_R^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x), I_R^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$ and $F_R^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$ for all $x, y \in E$
3. transitive if $R \circ R \subseteq R$.
4. neutrosophic refined equivalence relation if the relation R satisfies reflexive, symmetric and transitive.

Definition 3.10 The transitive closure of a neutrosophic refined relation R on $E \times E$ is $\tilde{R} = R \tilde{U} R^2 \tilde{U} R^3 \tilde{U} \dots$

Definition 3.11 If R is a neutrosophic refined relation from A to B then R^{-1} is the inverse neutrosophic refined relation R from B to A , defined as follows:

$$R^{-1} = \left\{ \left\langle (y, x), T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y), I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y), F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) \right\rangle : (x, y) \in E \times E \right\}$$

where

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x), I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x), F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x) \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Proposition 3.12 If R and S are two neutrosophic refined relation from A to B and B to C , respectively. Then,

1. $(R^{-1})^{-1} = R$

$$2. (S \circ R)^{-1} = R^{-1} \circ S^{-1}$$

Proof

1. Since R^{-1} is a neutrosophic refined relation from B to A, we have

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x), I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x) \text{ and } F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

Then,

$$T_{(R^{-1})^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) = T_R^j(x, y),$$

$$I_{(R^{-1})^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) = I_R^j(x, y)$$

and

$$F_{(R^{-1})^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) = F_R^j(x, y)$$

therefore $(R^{-1})^{-1} = R$.

2. If the composition $S \circ R$ is a neutrosophic refined relation from A to C, then the composition $R^{-1} \circ S^{-1}$ is a neutrosophic refined relation from C to A. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} T_{(S \circ R)^{-1}}^j(z, x) &= T_{(S \circ R)}^j(x, z) \\ &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_R^j(x, y) \wedge T_S^j(y, z) \right\} \\ &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \wedge T_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\}, \\ &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \wedge T_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= T_{R^{-1} \circ S^{-1}}^j(z, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{(S \circ R)^{-1}}^j(z, x) &= I_{(S \circ R)}^j(x, z) \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_R^j(x, y) \vee I_S^j(y, z) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \vee I_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \vee I_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= I_{R^{-1} \circ S^{-1}}^j(z, x) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{(S \circ R)^{-1}}^j(z, x) &= F_{(S \circ R)}^j(x, z) \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_R^j(x, y) \vee F_S^j(y, z) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \vee F_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_{S^{-1}}^j(z, y) \vee F_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= F_{R^{-1} \circ S^{-1}}^j(z, x) \end{aligned}$$

Finally; proof is valid.

Proposition 3.13 *If R is symmetric ,then R^{-1} is also symmetric.*

Proof: Assume that R is Symmetric then we have

$$T_R^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x),$$

$$I_R^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_R^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

Also if R^{-1} is an inverse relation, then we have

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x),$$

$$I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

for all $x, y \in E$

To prove R^{-1} is symmetric, it is enough to prove

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x),$$

$$I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x)$$

for all $x, y \in E$

Therefore;

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x) = T_R^j(x, y) = T_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x);$$

$$I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x) = I_R^j(x, y) = I_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x) = F_R^j(x, y) = F_{R^{-1}}^j(y, x)$$

Finally; proof is valid.

Proposition 3.14 *If R is symmetric ,if and only if $R = R^{-1}$.*

Proof: Let R be symmetric , then

$$T_R^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x);$$

$$I_R^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_R^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

and

R^{-1} is an inverse relation, then

$$T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x);$$

$$I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

for all $x, y \in E$

Therefore; $T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x) = T_R^j(x, y)$.

Similarly

$$I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x) = I_R^j(x, y)$$

and

$$F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x) = F_R^j(x, y)$$

for all $x, y \in E$.

Hence $R = R^{-1}$

Conversely, assume that $R = R^{-1}$ then, we have

$$T_R^j(x, y) = T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x).$$

Similarly

$$I_R^j(x, y) = I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_R^j(x, y) = F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x).$$

Hence R is symmetric.

Proposition 3.15 *If R and S are symmetric neutrosophic refined relations, then*

1. $R \tilde{\cup} S$,
2. $R \tilde{\cap} S$,
3. $R \tilde{+} S$
4. $R \tilde{\times} S$

are also symmetric.

Proof: R is symmetric, then we have;

$$T_R^j(x, y) = T_R^j(y, x),$$

$$I_R^j(x, y) = I_R^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_R^j(x, y) = F_R^j(y, x)$$

similarly S is symmetric, then we have

$$T_S^j(x, y) = T_S^j(y, x),$$

$$I_S^j(x, y) = I_S^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_S^j(x, y) = F_S^j(y, x)$$

Therefore,

1.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R\cup S}^j(x, y) &= \max \left\{ T_R^j(x, y), T_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ T_R^j(y, x), T_S^j(y, x) \right\}, \\ &= T_{R\cup S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{R\cup S}^j(x, y) &= \min \left\{ I_R^j(x, y), I_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ I_R^j(y, x), I_S^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= I_{R\cup S}^j(y, x), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{R\cup S}^j(x, y) &= \min \left\{ F_R^j(x, y), F_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ F_R^j(y, x), F_S^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= F_{R\cup S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

therefore, $R\cup S$ is symmetric.

2.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &= \min \left\{ T_R^j(x, y), T_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \min \left\{ T_R^j(y, x), T_S^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= T_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(y, x), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &= \max \left\{ I_R^j(x, y), I_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ I_R^j(y, x), I_S^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= I_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(y, x), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &= \max \left\{ F_R^j(x, y), F_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ &= \max \left\{ F_R^j(y, x), F_S^j(y, x) \right\} \\ &= F_{R\tilde{\cap} S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

therefore; $R\tilde{\cap} S$ is symmetric.

3.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) &= T_R^j(x, y) + T_S^j(x, y) - T_R^j(x, y)T_S^j(x, y) \\ &= T_R^j(y, x) + T_S^j(y, x) - T_R^j(y, x)T_S^j(y, x) \\ &= T_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) &= I_R^j(x, y)I_S^j(x, y) \\ &= I_R^j(y, x)I_S^j(y, x) \\ &= I_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) &= F_R^j(x, y)F_S^j(x, y) \\ &= F_R^j(y, x)F_S^j(y, x) \\ &= F_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

therefore, $R\tilde{+}S$ is also symmetric

4.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= T_R^j(x, y)T_S^j(x, y) \\ &= T_R^j(y, x)T_S^j(y, x) \\ &= T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= I_R^j(x, y) + I_S^j(x, y) - I_R^j(x, y)I_S^j(x, y) \\ &= I_R^j(y, x) + I_S^j(y, x) - I_R^j(y, x)I_S^j(y, x) \\ &= I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= F_R^j(x, y) + F_S^j(x, y) - F_R^j(x, y)F_S^j(x, y) \\ &= F_R^j(y, x) + F_S^j(y, x) - F_R^j(y, x)F_S^j(y, x) \\ &= F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(y, x) \end{aligned}$$

hence, $R\tilde{\times}S$ is also symmetric.

Remark 3.16 $R\circ S$ in general is not symmetric, as

$$\begin{aligned} T_{(R\circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_S^j(x, y) \wedge T_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\ &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_S^j(y, x) \wedge T_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\ &\neq T_{(R\circ S)}^j(z, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{(R\circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_S^j(x, y) \vee I_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_S^j(y, x) \vee I_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\ &\neq I_{(R\circ S)}^j(z, x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{(R \circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_S^j(x, y) \vee F_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_S^j(y, x) \vee F_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&\neq F_{(R \circ S)}^j(z, x)
\end{aligned}$$

but $R \circ S$ is symmetric, if $R \circ S = S \circ R$, for R and S are symmetric relations.

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{(R \circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_S^j(x, y) \wedge T_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\
&= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_S^j(y, x) \wedge T_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= \bigvee_y \left\{ T_R^j(y, x) \wedge T_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= T_{(R \circ S)}^j(z, x)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{(R \circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_S^j(x, y) \vee I_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_S^j(y, x) \vee I_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_y \left\{ I_R^j(y, x) \vee I_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= I_{(R \circ S)}^j(z, x)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
F_{(R \circ S)}^j(x, z) &= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_S^j(x, y) \vee F_R^j(y, z) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_S^j(y, x) \vee F_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_y \left\{ F_R^j(y, x) \vee F_R^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= F_{(R \circ S)}^j(z, x)
\end{aligned}$$

for every $(x, z) \in E \times E$ and for $y \in E$.

Proposition 3.17 *If R is transitive relation, then R^{-1} is also transitive.*

Proof : R is transitive relation, if $R \circ R \subseteq R$, hence if $R^{-1} \circ R^{-1} \subseteq R^{-1}$, then R^{-1} is transitive.

Consider;

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) &= T_R^j(y, x) \geq T_{R \circ R}^j(y, x) \\
&= \bigvee_z \left\{ T_R^j(y, z) \wedge T_R^j(z, x) \right\} \\
&= \bigvee_z \left\{ T_{R^{-1}}^j(x, z) \wedge T_{R^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= T_{R^{-1} \circ R^{-1}}^j(x, y)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) &= I_R^j(y, x) \leq I_{R \circ R}^j(y, x) \\
&= \bigwedge_z \left\{ I_R^j(y, z) \vee I_R^j(z, x) \right\} \\
&= \bigwedge_z \left\{ I_{R^{-1}}^j(x, z) \vee I_{R^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\} \\
&= I_{R^{-1} \circ R^{-1}}^j(x, y)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, y) &= F_R^j(y, x) \leq F_{R \circ R}^j(y, x) \\ &= \bigwedge_z \left\{ F_R^j(y, z) \vee F_R^j(z, x) \right\} \\ &= \bigwedge_z \left\{ F_{R^{-1}}^j(x, z) \vee F_{R^{-1}}^j(z, y) \right\} \\ &= F_{R^{-1} \circ R^{-1}}^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

hence, proof is valid.

Proposition 3.18 *If R is transitive relation, then $R \cap S$ is also transitive*

Proof: As R and S are transitive relations, $R \circ R \subseteq R$ and $S \circ S \subseteq S$. also

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R \tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &\geq T_{(R \tilde{\cap} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cap} S)}^j(x, y) \\ I_{R \tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &\leq I_{(R \tilde{\cap} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cap} S)}^j(x, y) \\ F_{R \tilde{\cap} S}^j(x, y) &\leq F_{(R \tilde{\cap} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cap} S)}^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

implies $R \tilde{\cap} S \circ (R \tilde{\cap} S) \subseteq R \cap S$, hence $R \cap S$ is transitive.

Proposition 3.19 *If R and S are transitive relations, then*

1. $R \tilde{\cup} S$,
2. $R \tilde{+} S$
3. $R \tilde{\times} S$

are not transitive.

Proof:

1. As

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) &= \max \left\{ T_R^j(x, y), T_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ I_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) &= \min \left\{ I_R^j(x, y), I_S^j(x, y) \right\} \\ F_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) &= \min \left\{ F_R^j(x, y), F_S^j(x, y) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} T_{(R \tilde{\cup} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cup} S)}^j(x, y) &\geq T_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) \\ I_{(R \tilde{\cup} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cup} S)}^j(x, y) &\leq I_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) \\ F_{(R \tilde{\cup} S) \circ (R \tilde{\cup} S)}^j(x, y) &\leq F_{R \tilde{\cup} S}^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

2. As

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R \tilde{+} S}^j(x, y) &= T_R^j(x, y) + T_S^j(x, y) - T_R^j(x, y)T_S^j(x, y) \\ I_{R \tilde{+} S}^j(x, y) &= I_R^j(x, y)I_S^j(x, y) \\ F_{R \tilde{+} S}^j(x, y) &= F_R^j(x, y)F_S^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} T_{(R\tilde{+}S)\circ(R\tilde{+}S)}^j(x, y) &\geq T_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) \\ I_{(R\tilde{+}S)\circ(R\tilde{+}S)}^j(x, y) &\leq I_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) \\ F_{(R\tilde{+}S)\circ(R\tilde{+}S)}^j(x, y) &\leq F_{R\tilde{+}S}^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

3. As

$$\begin{aligned} T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= T_R^j(x, y)T_S^j(x, y) \\ I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= I_R^j(x, y) + I_S^j(x, y) - I_R^j(x, y)I_S^j(x, y) \\ F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) &= F_R^j(x, y) + F_S^j(x, y) - F_R^j(x, y)F_S^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} T_{(R\tilde{\times}S)\circ(R\tilde{\times}S)}^j(x, y) &\geq T_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) \\ I_{(R\tilde{\times}S)\circ(R\tilde{\times}S)}^j(x, y) &\leq I_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) \\ F_{(R\tilde{\times}S)\circ(R\tilde{\times}S)}^j(x, y) &\leq F_{R\tilde{\times}S}^j(x, y) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $R\tilde{U}S$, $R\tilde{+}S$ and $R\tilde{\times}S$ are not transitive.

Proposition 3.20 *If R is transitive relation, then R^2 is also transitive.*

Proof: R is transitive relation, if $R \circ R \subseteq R$, therefore if $R^2 \circ R^{-2} \subseteq R^2$, then R^2 is transitive.

$$T_{R\circ R}^j(y, x) = \underset{z}{\vee} \left\{ T_R^j(y, z) \wedge T_R^j(z, x) \right\} \geq \underset{z}{\vee} \left\{ T_{R\circ R}^j(y, z) \wedge T_{R\circ R}^j(z, x) \right\} = T_{R^2\circ R^2}^j(y, x),$$

$$I_{R\circ R}^j(y, x) = \underset{z}{\wedge} \left\{ I_R^j(y, z) \vee I_R^j(z, x) \right\} \leq \underset{z}{\wedge} \left\{ I_{R\circ R}^j(y, z) \vee I_{R\circ R}^j(z, x) \right\} = I_{R^2\circ R^2}^j(y, x)$$

and

$$F_{R\circ R}^j(y, x) = \underset{z}{\wedge} \left\{ F(y, z) \vee F_R^j(z, x) \right\} \leq \underset{z}{\wedge} \left\{ I_{R\circ R}^j(y, z) \vee F_{R\circ R}^j(z, x) \right\} = F_{R^2\circ R^2}^j(y, x)$$

Finally, the proof is valid.

4 Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the anonymous reviewer for their careful reading of this research paper and for their helpful comments.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have firstly defined the neutrosophic refined relations(NRR). The NRR are the extension of neutrosophic relation (NR) and intuitionistic multirelation[27]. The notions of inverse, symmetry, reflexivity and transitivity on neutrosophic refined relations are studied. The future work will cover the application of the NRR in decision making, pattern recognition and in medical diagnosis.

References

- [1] A.Q. Ansari, R. Biswas and S. Aggarwal, Proposal for Applicability of Neutrosophic Set Theory in Medical AI, *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 27/5 (2011) 5–11.
- [2] A. Kharal, *A Neutrosophic Multicriteria Decision Making Method*, New Mathematics and Natural Computation, Creighton University, USA, 2013.
- [3] A.Q. Ansari, R. Biswas and S. Aggarwal, Neutrosophic classifier: An extension of fuzzy classifier, *Applied Soft Computing* 13 (2013) 563–573.
- [4] A. Syropoulos, On generalized fuzzy multisets and their use in computation, *Iranian Journal Of Fuzzy Systems* 9(2) (2012) 113–125.
- [5] A. S. Thomas and S. J. John, Multi-fuzzy rough sets and relations, *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics* x/x (2013) xx-xxx.
- [6] C. Ashbacher, *Introduction to Neutrosophic Logic*, American Research Press Rehoboth 2002.
- [7] C. S. Calude, G. Paun, G. Rozenberg, A. Salomaa, *Lecture notes in computer science: Multiset Processing Mathematical, Computer Science, and Molecular Computing Points of View*, 2235, (2001) Springer-New York.
- [8] D. Rabounski F. Smarandache L. Borissova *Neutrosophic Methods in General Relativity*, *Hexis*, No:10 (2005).
- [9] F. G. Lupiáñez, On neutrosophic topology, *Kybernetes*, 37(6) (2008) 797–800.
- [10] F. Smarandache, *A Unifying Field in Logics. Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set and Logic*, Rehoboth: American Research Press (1998).
- [11] F. Smarandache, *n-Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics*, *Progress in Physics*, 143-146, Vol. 4, 2013.
- [12] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y. Q. Zhang and R. Sunderraman, Single valued neutrosophic sets, *Multispace and Multistructure* 4 (2010) 410-413.
- [13] I. Deli and S. Broumi, *Neutrosophic multisets and its application in medical diagnosis* (2014) (submitted)
- [14] I. Deli, *Interval-valued neutrosophic soft sets and its decision making* <http://arxiv.org/abs/1402.3130>.
- [15] I. Deli, Y. Toktas and S. Broumi, *Relations on Neutrosophic Parameterized Soft Sets and Their Applications*, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 3, 2014.

- [16] I. Deli, Y. Toktas, and S. Broumi. Neutrosophic Parameterized Soft relations and Their Application Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 4, 2014, pp.25-34.
- [17] K. T. Atanassov, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 20(1), 87–86, 1986.
- [18] L. A. Zadeh, Fuzzy Sets, Inform. and Control, 8 (1965) 338-353.
- [19] M. Dhar, S. Broumi and F. Smarandache. A Note on Square Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices, Neutrosophic sets and systems, Vol 3.(2014) 37-41
- [20] M. Arora and R. Biswas, Deployment of Neutrosophic Technology to Retrieve Answers for Queries Posed in Natural Language, 3. Int. Conf. on Comp. Sci. and Inform. Tech. (2010) 435–439.
- [21] M. Arora, R. Biswas and U.S. Pandey, Neutrosophic Relational Database Decomposition, International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, 2(8) (2011) 121–125.
- [22] P.K. Maji, Neutrosophic soft set, Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics, 5/ 1 (2013) 157-168.
- [23] P. A. Ejegwa, J. A. Awolola, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multiset (IFMS) In Binomial Distributions, International Journal Of Scientific and Technology Research 3(4) (2014) 335-337.
- [24] P. Chi and L. Peide, An Extended TOPSIS Method for the Multiple Attribute Decision Making Problems Based on Interval Neutrosophic, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems 1 (2013) 63-70.
- [25] P. Rajarajeswari and N. Uma, On Distance and Similarity Measures of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Set, IOSR Journal of Mathematics 5(4) (2013) 19–23.
- [26] P. Rajarajeswari and N. Uma, A Study of Normalized Geometric and Normalized Hamming Distance Measures in Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Sets, International Journal of Science and Research, Engineering and Technology 2(11) (2013) 76–80.
- [27] P. Rajarajeswari, N. Uma, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Relations, International Journal of Mathematical Archives 4(10) (2013) 244-249.
- [28] P. Rajarajeswari and N. Uma, Zhang and Fu's Similarity Measure on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Sets, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology 3(5) (2014) 12309–12317.
- [29] P. Rajarajeswari, N. Uma, Correlation Measure For Intuitionistic Fuzzy Multi Sets, International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology 3(1) (2014) 611-617.

- [30] R. Muthuraj and S. Balamurugan, Multi-Fuzzy Group and its Level Subgroups, *Gen. Math. Notes* 17(1) (2013) 74-81.
- [31] R. R. Yager, On the theory of bags (Multi sets), *Int. J. Of General System*, 13 (1986) 23–37.
- [32] S. Aggarwal, R. Biswas and A. Q. Ansari, Neutrosophic Modeling and Control, *Computer and Communication Technology* (2010) 718–723.
- [33] S. Broumi and F. Smarandache, Intuitionistic Neutrosophic Soft Set, *Journal of Information and Computing Science*, 8(2) (2013) 130–140.
- [34] S. Broumi, Generalized Neutrosophic Soft Set, *International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology* 3(2) (2013) 17–30.
- [35] S. Broumi, F. Smarandache, Several Similarity Measures of Neutrosophic Sets, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 1 (2013) 54–62.
- [36] S. Broumi, F. Smarandache, More on Intuitionistic Neutrosophic Soft Sets, *Computer Science and Information Technology* 1(4) (2013) 257-268.
- [37] S. Broumi, I. Deli and F. Smarandache, Relations on Interval Valued Neutrosophic Soft Sets, *Journal of New Results in Science*, 5 (2014) 1–20.
- [38] S. Broumi, I. Deli, F. Smarandache Neutrosophic Parametrized Soft Set theory and its decision making problem, *International Frontier Science Letter*, Vol. 1, No. 1, (2014) 1-11.
- [39] S. Broumi, M. Dhar, F. Smarandache, Rough neutrosophic sets, *Italian journal of pure and applied mathematics*, No. 32, (2014) 493502
- [40] S. Broumi, F. Smarandache, Lower and Upper Soft Interval Valued Neutrosophic Rough Approximations of An IVNSS-Relation, *Proceedings of SISOM ACOUSTICS 2014 International Conference, Bucharest, 22-23 May 2014*, pp. 204-211.
- [41] S. Broumi and F Smarandache, On Neutrosophic Implications. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 2, (2014) 9-17
- [42] S. Broumi, I. Deli and F. Smarandache, Interval Valued Neutrosophic Parameterized Soft Set Theory and its Decision Making, *Journal of New Results in Science*, No7, (2014) 58-71
- [43] S. Das, M. B. Kar and S. Kar, Group multi-criteria decision making using intuitionistic multi-fuzzy sets, *Journal of Uncertainty Analysis and Applications* 10(1) (2013) 1-16.
- [44] S. Sebastian and T. V. Ramakrishnan, Multi-fuzzy Subgroups, *Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sciences* 6(8) (2011) 365–372.

- [45] S. Sebastian and T. V. Ramakrishnan, Multi-fuzzy extension of crisp functions using bridge functions, *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics* 2(1) (2011) 1–8.
- [46] S. Sebastian and T. V. Ramakrishnan, Multi-Fuzzy Sets, *International Mathematical Forum* 5(50) (2010) 2471–2476.
- [47] T. K. Shinoj and S. J. John, Intuitionistic fuzzy multisets and its application in medical diagnosis, *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology* 6 (2012) 01–28.
- [48] V. Kandasamy and F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic Lattices, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 2, (2014) 42-47
- [49] Z. Pawlak, Rough sets, *Int. J. Comput. Inform. Sci.*, 11 (1982) 341–356.